

Scientometric Study of Emerging Technologies in Library and Information Science

Dr. Vaishali M. Chaudhari

Gmail : cvaishali1306@gmail.com

Librarian (Professor)

Lal Bahadur Shastri college Partur, Dist. Jalna

Miss. Pratibha Dagdu Waghmare

Ph.D.(Student)

Dept. of Library & Information Science

Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad

Gmail: waghmarepratibha91@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The present study of bibliometric of study of digital transformation libraries for five years from 2018-2022 Total 432 published articles were of articles, degree of collaboration, and articles has been done. Inferences has been drawn from the analysis that Journal Articles were found most prevalent source of information for The eight bibliometric tools Year wise contribution , No. of Authors wise contribution, Document Types of contribution, AGR, Institute Types of Documents have been used for the data analysis

Key word: Emerging Technologies Library And Information Science

1.Introduction

Scientometrics is the science of measuring and analyzing science. In practice, Scientometrics is often done using Bibliometrics which is a measurement of the impact of (scientific) publications. Scientometrics is the science of method scientific output similar to Bibliometrics used by librarians and information scientist. (Agrawal, aruna, 1982); related fields are the history of science and technology philosophy of science and sociology of scientific knowledge. (Eugene Garfield, 1995) ; application of mathematical and statistical methods of scientific literature (Derek de solla, 2000) ; to identify national an international network and to map the development of new fields of science and technology as well as to know the inner logic of science development (yadavJaisi Ram, 1984) ; this enables to evaluate the size of scientific production on the assumption that the essence of scientific activity is the assumption the production of knowledge (Eugene Garfield, 2002); open access has emerged in the last few years as serious alternative to additional commercial publishing models taking the benefits offered by technology one step further (Wasudevan K T 1995); one significant finding in the field is principle of cost escalation to the effect that achieving further findings at a given level of importance grow exponentially more costly in the expenditure of efforts and resources (Manavalan R 1982) ; other characteristics of open access journals are that author relation copyrights and they must self achieved content in an independent repository (David Wilson, 2001); modern Scientometrics is mostly based in latter founded the institute for scientific information which is heavily used for Scientometric analysis (Derek, J. 1995); currently prepares and international methodological manual that

will contain guidelines for creating applying and interpreting the indices based on Bibliometric data (Eva Rodenas, 2001).

1.2 Definition Analysis:

1.2.1 Scientometrics:

According to bankapur, M.B. and Kumara, (1993) “Scientometric is a more general than Bibliometrics. It is interesting to know, that both disciplines have a large overlap. It is surprised to learn certain comments stating that both disciplines have a large overlap. It is surprised to learn certain comments stating that Scientometric, using Bibliometrics techniques is a part of Bibliometrics”.

1.2.2 Scientometric Analysis:

According to (2006), wouters, a correlation has always existed between academic Scientometric and political /practical, Scientometric, the latter of which has been described as a hybrid of social science and business expertise (2006).

Web of science Data Base

A rich collection of citation indexes representing the citation connections between scholarly research articles found in the most globally significant journals, books, and proceedings in the sciences, social sciences, and art & humanities. The Web of Science Core Collection serves as the standard data set underpinning the journal impact metrics found in the Journal Citation Reports and the institutional performance metrics found in In Cite

About Emerging technology

Emerging technology is a term generally used to describe a new technology, but it may also refer to the continuing development of an existing technology it can have slightly different meaning when used in different areas, such as media, business, science, or education.

Libraries are universally recognized as important social institutions and no community is considered complete without a library system. However, libraries are facing change due to impact of ICT, changing patron needs, changing information environment or Web/Google that is trying to replace Reference Librarians. Use of Disruptive technologies is resulting in transition from Print to Digital, Changes takes place from Forms to Formats, Delivery systems, and it is inevitable

There is a transformation in the need of library users and due to ICT, there is a change in the resources, services and products of the libraries. Every institution is now trying to compete in the national and international rankings and with the changed roles and services; the libraries and librarians are playing key role.

Libraries in developed countries have been using emerging technologies like Robotics, Cloud Computing, RFID, Big Data, Institutional Repositories, Virtual and Augmented Reality, Book Delivery Drones, and Web 2.0 to provide library and information services.

1.4 Review of Literature

Scientometric / Bibliometric / Citation studies have done earlier by different authors on the different individual journal publications and literature on specific subject areas. The following studies related to the objectives of this study have been reviewed.

Srimurugan A & Natter S analyzed the D-LIB magazine published during 2000 –2007 which revealed that highest number of papers was published in 2005 and the lowest in 2007.

Dr. Vaishali Khaparde, Pratibha D Waghmar (2024), The study is based on the Scientometric analysis of 355 research Journal published on Article of Library Science during the periods of 2019-2023. This Study will review on length of the title, numbers of pages, type of document, distribution of article, no of references print as well as webreferences authorship pattern, the findings must reveal various aspects of the characteristics and patterns of contributions of the study.

Shilpa Kachru Tupe, Dr. Vaishali S. Khaparde(2019), Stem cells are self-renewing cells with the ability to differentiate into a variety of cells and are viewed to have great potential in the field of regenerative medicine. The study is based on the Scientometric evaluation of 159 publications published on Stem cell & regenerative medicine Journals among German society during the period of 2009 -2018. The six scientometric tools Annual Growth Rate (AGR), collaborative index (CI), collaboration coefficient (CC), Degree of collaboration (DC), Relative Growth Rate (RGR) and Doubling Time (DT) and Type of Documents have been used for the data analysis.

Miss. Pratibha Dagdu Waghmare¹, Dr. Vaishali M. Chaudhari (2023). The study is based on the Scientometric analysis of 207 research Journal published on Article Of Library Science during the periods of 2018-2022. This Study will review on length of the title, numbers of pages, type of document, distribution of article, no of references print as well as web references authorship pattern, The findings must reveal various aspects of the characteristics and patterns of contributions of the study

SCOPE AND LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The present study is based on the Scientometric Analysis of Scientometric Study of Emerging Technologies in Library And Information Science. The present study is based on over all 432 articles during 2018-2022.

DATA COLLECTION

Data can be numerically expressed that is quantified quantifiable or objective (Fayol and Daly, 1990) the data was collected from and Analysis with the use of spss package Scientometric Study of Emerging Technologies in Library And Information Science.

V. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Scientometric analysis is a branch of bibliometrics. It is an important research tool for understanding the subject it aims at measuring the utility of documents and relationship between documents and fields.

Objectives of the Study

1. Year wise contribution of distribution.
2. No. of Authors wise contribution of distributions
3. To estimate the annual growth rate (AGR) of publications
4. Document types of distribution of contributions
5. Institutes wise contribution of distributions.

1. Year wise Distribution of contribution Year wise

Distribution of contributions is shown in Table No 1

Table No 1

Sr. No	YEAR	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	2018	81	18.75
2	2019	78	18.06
3	2020	70	16.20
4	2021	101	23.38
5	2022	102	23.61
	Total	432	100.00

It can be observed from the table No. 1 & Figure no. 1 out of the total 432 contributions majority of the Contributions i.e. 81 contributions were contributed in 2018 were as inimum contributions i.e. (18.75%)in contusions 2019, 78 (18.06%)contributions 2020, 70(16.20%)were Contributed in2021 101 (23.38%) contributions were contributed 2022i.e. 102 (23.61%).

Fig No-1

2. Table no-2 Authorship Pattern of contribution of distribution The Authorship pattern of contributions is shown in Table No. Table No-2

Table No. Table No-2

Sr. No	No. of Authors	Frequency	Percentage
1	First Author	81	18.75
2	Second Authors	78	18.06
3	Three Authors	70	16.20
4	Four Authors	101	23.38
5	Five & more than Authors	102	23.61
	Total	432	100.00

Table N o -2 and Authorship pattern of contributions The distribution of Authorship pattern is given in the Table No.2. The table shows that co authorship is predominant then single

authors. Table No. 2 & 2 indicates that majority of the contributions are contributed by co authors.

Fig No-2

2. Table No- 3 To estimate the annual growth rate (AGR) of publications
To estimate the annual growth rate (AGR) of publications

Table No- 3

Year	Volume	Total no. of publications	AGR %
2018	14	81	
2019	11	78	-3.70
2020	6	70	-10.26
2021	14	101	44.29
2022	6	102	0.99
Total	51	432	323.53

The growth rate is a measurement which is essential in any field. In meaning the growth of the number of publications in a particular discipline, this is often a measure of the annual increase or decrease. Here, the AGR has been determined as per the formula given below.

$$AGR = \frac{\text{End value} - \text{First Value}}{\text{First Value}} \times 100$$

In this study, the end value is 2018 in the year , 2021the first value is 101 in the year .Table 3 shows that the year on the change in the number of documents was -44% in 2021, 0.99% over the respective next year.

Fig. No.3 Annual Growth rate (AGR)

4. Table No- 4 Types of Document Contribution of Distribution
Types of Document of contributions is shown in Table

No. Table No- 4

Sr. No	Document Types	Frequency	Percentage
1	Article	269	59.65
2	Book Chapter	5	1.11
3	Article; Early Access	5	1.11
4	Proceedings Paper	60	13.30
5	Review	93	20.62
	Total	432	95.79

Table no. 4 and figure no. 4 Shows that, the highest 269 (59.65 %) number of publication has been published inOriginal article in these study, Feature (0.39%), Reviews93(20.62%) and Proceedings Paper 60(13.30%) and Books Chapter 5 (1.11%) etc. is analyzed

Fig No .4

Table No- 5 Institution wise Contribution of Distribution
Institution wise of contributions is shown in Table No.

Table No- 5

Sr. No	Nmae of Institute	Frequency	Percentage
1	Department	2	0.46
2	Institute	24	5.56
3	Organisation	1	0.23
4	University	402	93.06
5	NA	3	0.69
	Total	432	100.00

Table No. 5 depicts the distribution of contributions, University wise at the national level followed institution and Department . It is inferred from the above table that university wise contribution maximum is no is 402 were Institute 24 contribution and Department contribution of Department is 2.

Fig. No-5 Institution wise

VI. FINDING

1. The highest numbers 102 (23.61%) of papers were published in 2022 contributing.
2. More than two-thirds 102 (23.61%) of papers were contributed by multiple authors.
3. Estimate the annual growth rate (AGR) of publications high i.e 2022 102,(0.99%).
4. Document Type distribution of the contribution article is high. i.e. frequency 2 with 269(59.65%).and is lowest document type are Books chapter 2,(1.11 %)
5. The Institution of high frequency i.e university 402(93..06%) lowest i.e. Department .institution is 2.(0.46%)

CONCLUSION

Scientometric relatively new subject of information. It helps to evaluate information & to handle the information in libraries and information centers by the quantitative analyzed information. It deals with the mathematical and statistical analysis. This is an umbrella term used for many studies where quantitative method or techniques are used to investigate various aspect of written document. Scientometric study of Emerging Technologies of library and information science. as published in highly ranked journals, as well as to detect any lack of knowledge on relevant issues . The results of the literature review showed that the Our results do not allow us to draw statistical conclusions; however, this was not the aim of our

survey. ETCs are important, yet they are not without major risks. Manufacturers should help colorectal surgeons to convey the right message to patients.

References

3. Hussain, A., & Fatima, N. (2017). *Emerging Trends in Information Technology in Modern Libraries*. Manakin Press.
4. Bankapur, M.B. & Kumar (1993): Job satisfaction and publication output among librarians in Nigerian Universities. *Library Management*. 20(1), 39-48
5. Derek, De.Solla. (2000). A study of learning and retention with a web-based IR interface *journal of librarianship and information science* 37(1), pp.7-16.
6. Eva, Rodents. (2001), Advanced bibliometrics method as quantitative core of peer review based evaluation and foresight exercises, *Scientometrics*, 36(1)397-420
7. Fasibs off and Dely (1990), Federal research impact assessment: Axioms, approaches, applications, *Scientometrics*, 34(1)163-206.
8. Wasudevan, K.T., (1995). Data sources for performing citation Analysis; an overview. *Journal of Documentation*. 64(20), 193-210.
9. Wouters, (2006). *Scientometrics Analysis*. *Journal of Library and Information Technology*. 1(1), 5-9
10. Pratibha D Waghmar, Dr. Vaishali Khaparde, (2024), *Scientometric profile of library resource sharing* *International Journal of Academic Research and Development* 2024, Published: 03-02-2024 Volume 9, Issue 1, 2024, Page No. 33-38
11. Shilpa Kachru Tupe, Dr. Vaishali S. Khaparde (2019), A SCIENTOMETRIC EVALUATION OF PUBLICATIONS IN STEM CELL REGENERATIVE MEDICINE JOURNALS AMONG GERMAN SOCIETY 2009 – 2018, *International Journal of Library & Information Science (IJLIS)* Volume 8, Issue 3, September - December 2019, pp. 16-25, Article ID: IJLIS_08_03_003 Available online at
12. Miss. Pratibha Dagdu Waghmare, Dr. Vaishali M. Chaudhari (2023), *Scientometric Study Of Techniques In Coloproctology*, *IJSART - Volume 9 Issue 12 – DECEMBER 2023* ISSN [ONLINE]: 2395-1052.